

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

D3.6 Multi-site research design and methodological framework (update)

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Executive Summary

The empirical research conducted in the COVINFORM project is centred around assessing COVID-19 impact, response, and lessons learned across diverse local contexts. This includes an exploration of how national and local COVID-19 responses have impacted human behaviour, social dynamics, economic well-being, and physical and mental health outcomes; how local responses to COVID-19 were adapted to and shaped by the local health, socioeconomic, political and community contexts; and which policy failures, unintended consequences, trade-offs and promising practices can be identified in COVID-19 responses.

This report presents deliverable 3.6 (D3.6), which provides an update on the project's empirical research, including the overall case study framework and methodology presented in D3.2. This deliverable's goals include outlining the finished and ongoing empirical research, incorporating it into the theoretical framework, and going over the methodological experiences thus far. We review the overarching theoretical framework in the deliverable's first section. The discussion of the project-level research goals and questions will centre on how they are modified and further defined for the COVINFORM project. Then we delve further into the completed empirical cross-WP resident interviews and the ongoing fieldwork of the case studies of WP3. Methodological reflections will be established, addressing the difficulties and achievements of the research conducted so far. Finally, an indication of the project's guidelines for (comparative) data analysis is provided.

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

Term	Description
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BAME	Black, Asian and Minority Ethnic
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
D.	Deliverable.
DOA	Description of Action
EU	European Union
LTCF	Long Term Care Facility
RQ	Research Question
SES	Socio Economic Status
SMU	Sub Municipal Unit
WHO	World Health Organisation
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

Since its emergence in December 2019, the COVID-19 pandemic has had enormous social, behavioural and economic consequences around the globe. The effects of the COVID-19 pandemic go far beyond physical health, impacting individuals' and communities' everyday lives and well-being, including in the domains of mental health, employment, education, and community dynamics. However, the pandemic has not disrupted everybody's lives in the same way. Some groups and individuals are disproportionately exposed to the COVID-19 virus and experience more negative impacts of the COVID-19 measures. COVID-19 has exposed pre-existing social fault lines in societies (Kawachi, 2020). The pandemic is socially patterned not just in terms of COVID-19 morbidity and mortality rates, but also in terms of the consequences of the implemented restrictions and emergency lockdown measures (Bambra et al., 2020).

Using a multidisciplinary and intersectional approach, the COVINFORM project examines how vulnerability is defined and addressed (if at all) in COVID-19 responses from government, public health and communication perspectives. The project also studies the differential impact that different national, regional, and local responses have had on vulnerable and marginalised groups. Ultimately, COVINFORM is developing solutions, guidelines and recommendations to ensure that the needs of vulnerable and marginalised groups are appropriately considered in potential waves of COVID-19 and future pandemics.

This report presents deliverable 3.6 (D3.6), an update of the overall case study framework and methodology presented in D3.2. The aim of this deliverable is to set out the completed and ongoing empirical research, integrate it within the theoretical framework and discuss the methodological experiences so far. In the first section of the deliverable, we revisit the overall theoretical framework as well as the project-level research questions, focusing on how they are reformulated and specified during the COVINFORM project. Then, we delve deeper into the completed empirical cross-WP resident interviews, as well as the ongoing fieldwork of the case studies of WP3. Methodological reflections will be established, exploring the challenges and successes of the research conducted so far. Finally, we highlight the next steps and provide some guidelines for the analysis of the resident interviews and case studies.

2 Theoretical framework

2.1 Revisiting complex systems theory and intersectionality theory

The COVINFORM project draws upon **complex adaptive system approaches** as well as **intersectional approaches** to offer a **multilevel and interdisciplinary critique of COVID-19 responses on the levels of government, public health, community, information & communications as well as resident perspective**. As we provided an extensive overview of both theories in D3.2., we aim to reflect more on how these theories guided us over the course of the research project. The main aim of the COVINFORM project is to understand 1) how pandemic responses were drafted, implemented and experienced. Here, our research interest also focuses on how these changed over time, and within the different dimensions of pandemic response (WP4-7). Further, the project investigates 2) how vulnerabilities were considered in the COVID-19 responses as well as 3) the impact of these responses on various vulnerable groups and **how these vulnerable groups navigate such barriers during the COVID-19 pandemic**.

Our theoretical framework builds on complex systems approaches that focus on the structure, interactions and dynamics of complex systems (Ostrom, 2007). We use a complex systems approach as a global framework to understand interactions across domains including public health, community response and governance. This approach helps to assess overall impacts and responses at an overarching systems level and to understand how different systems create certain outcomes (see D3.1 and D3.2 for a more detailed explanation).

Complex systems theory was also used to select and analyse the case studies (see D3.1, D3.5). A complex systems approach allows understanding of the vulnerability and resilience of different systems. Specifically, it helps to unravel how various systems ‘deal’ with COVID-19, how various sub-systems are interlocked within a larger system, and what this tells us about the systems’ resilience.

Further, we aim to study how specific vulnerable groups are impacted by COVID-19 responses and how they navigate this. In the COVINFORM project, we define vulnerability as “the conditions determined by physical, social, economic, and environmental factors or processes, which increase the susceptibility of [an individual or] a community to the impact of hazards” (UN/ISDR, Geneva 2004; cited in United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Reduction 2005). Further, the project understands vulnerability as relational (Habermas 2003). In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, the project has focused on vulnerabilities that are a consequence of (multiple) social disadvantages, exposure to the virus as well as health status. Social disadvantages are nonetheless on the foreground of our analysis as a higher level of exposure as well as health vulnerabilities are often closely connected with individuals occupying disadvantaged and marginalised social identity categories. This also explains why marginalised groups are disproportionately hit hard by, for example, pandemics (Singer et al. 2017). As such, the COVINFORM project frames the COVID-19 pandemic as more than a health crisis.

To understand the impact of disadvantage and marginalisation, the COVINFORM project uses intersectional approaches. Intersectionality emerged from the work of Black feminist scholars as a feminist, anti-racist approach to analyse the experience and struggles of multiple disadvantaged and marginalised groups (Sangaramoorthy & Benton 2022). The term intersectionality was coined by Kimberle Crenshaw’s (1991). In her article Mapping the Margins: Intersectionality, Identity Politics and Violence Against Women of Color, Crenshaw raises issues on the interaction of race and gender in the case of violence against Women of Colour (1991, p. 1296) and argues that social categories such as

race and gender, but also others, are mutually constitutive and cannot be thought of as additive. This means that the experience of people who are affected by multiple forms of oppression/disadvantage is not adequately understood if it is simply framed as the experience of, for example, racism and sexism. Intersectionality aims to highlight how multiple social categories reinforce each other and as such shape social and structural inequalities. By using intersectionality, the COVINFORM project explores how marginalised groups, including women from low socioeconomic backgrounds, experience the current pandemic, its response, and its impacts, considering that 'multiple axes of inequality constitute intersecting systems of oppression and privilege, resulting in a multitude of experiences, from interpersonal to community to institutional' (Sangaramoorthy & Benton 2022, p.2). By using an intersectional approach, the project wants to understand how broader and structural processes create certain vulnerabilities. Additionally, the project wants to ensure that its output considers the experience of marginalised and vulnerable groups.

The project uses intersectional approaches to understand the experience of vulnerable groups and when designing policy recommendations and other project outputs.

2.2 Reconsidering the research questions

Considering the research conducted so far in the COVINFORM project, we critically reflected on the research questions initially defined in the first year of the pandemic:

RQ1: How did national and local COVID-19 responses impact human behaviour, social dynamics,

economic wellbeing, and physical and mental health outcomes across diverse local contexts?

RQ2: How were local responses to COVID-19 adapted to and shaped by the local health, socioeconomic,

political and community contexts?

RQ3: Which policy failures, unintended consequences, trade-offs and promising practices can be

identified in COVID-19 responses across diverse local contexts?

Building further on progressive insights gained globally as well as based on our own empirical and theoretical work, we considered it relevant to adapt our focus to reflect the situation and defined the following research questions that will further guide us throughout the analyses of the COVINFORM project:

RQ1: How and under which conditions were COVID-19 responses drafted, implemented and experienced?

RQ2: How and in which ways was vulnerability considered in COVID-19 response?

RQ3: What were the lived experiences of the pandemic and its response within certain vulnerable groups?

RQ4: What were the different kinds of barriers and how were they managed?

RQ5: What are the lessons learned and promising practices that can be identified in COVID-19 responses across diverse local contexts?

By focusing on these five overarching research questions for the analysis of the WP3 case studies as well as for the analysis of the resident interviews collected for WP4-7, we aim to streamline the data analyses across the COVINFORM project. Moreover, exploring the answers to these redefined research questions will allow current and future policy makers to better deal with the needs of vulnerable groups that have been heavily affected during the COVID-19 pandemic as well as to better understand factors of vulnerability and resilience within systems, communities and individuals.

3 Structure of empirical research and research methodology

This section first provides an overview of the planned and conducted empirical research within the COVINFORM project, specifically concerning the cross-WP4-7 interviews with residents (citizens or community members) and the ongoing fieldwork of the case studies of WP3. Afterwards, an overview of conducted research will be given, with information on sampling and recruitment strategies.

3.1 Overview of conducted empirical research

For the baseline empirical research under WP4-7, interviews were undertaken with five governmental actors active in making or implementing policy, five health stakeholders active in providing public health services, five CSO representatives active, and five media and government communicators active in risk communications relevant (see D4.2, D5.2, D6.2, D7.2). Further, 12 residents were interviewed (see further down section ‘Resident Interviews’)

Additionally, 10 empirical case studies are conducted under WP3. These focus on a specific “vulnerable population”, i.e. a population group identified as vulnerable in policy documents and/or targeted with group-specific interventions, etc. The case studies aim to draw comparisons along the systems approach accompanying an in-depth, contextual understanding of each specific case. The case studies should complement the baseline empirical research.

Figure 1: Case studies complement resident interviews (empirical research WP4-7)

Resident Interviews

The COVINFORM research questions are centred around assessing COVID-19 impact, response, and lessons learned across the research sites and study populations. The consortium agreed that each of the WPs 4-7 would have minimum n=5 expert interviews in each study site with individuals that have specific knowledge in a certain (professional) field of action (Döringer, 2021). On top of this, it was planned to have minimum n=12 resident interviews in each research site, which are 'shared' between WPs 4-7. Subsequent project discussions in late 2021 resulted in the decision to focus the resident sample on women of low socioeconomic status (SES) as these are exposed to multiple vulnerabilities through their gender and SES. Sample sizes were chosen of n=12 per research site. A highly heterogeneous sample of n=12 would likely give quite disconnected insights, whereas with a narrowly defined sample we might still achieve some level of data saturation.

We wanted to choose a group that is relevant and comparable across national contexts. Low SES is consistently considered a risk factor or 'driver of vulnerability' across country contexts, which makes it a group that can suitably be compared across partner countries. Furthermore, some women face the 'double burden' of being a woman and living in systemic poverty. From an intersectional perspective, the impacts of the COVID-19 crisis have exacerbated both the gap between men and women, but also the economic and social differences within different groups of women. This is why we chose to focus on women within a lower SES.

In order to ensure resident interviews across countries are conducted in the same period, partners conducted the n=12 interviews in the period June-August 2022, with the deadline to submit the translated transcripts of the resident interviews 30 September 2022.

Case studies

This section also entails the description of the final 10 case studies of the COVINFORM project conducted by FS (Portugal), UANTWERP (Belgium), URJC & SAMUR (Spain), SAPIENZA & UCSC (Italy), SYNYO (Austria), SINUS & UGOT (Germany & Sweden), KEMEA (Greece), SWANSEA (Wales) and MDI (England). COVINFORM case studies aim to describe the diversity of COVID-19 impact in a huge array of contexts and vulnerable populations, and to be able to compare the dynamics of the different systems' response to the pandemics and protection of vulnerable groups across different geographical systems. In order to accomplish this, consistent theoretical and methodological frameworks had to be found and validated to enable the analysis of cumulative and synergic vulnerabilities across all case studies. All case studies have a particular focus on at least one of the following: low socio-economic status, gender, disabilities. Table 1 below gives a brief overview by vulnerable target population and the data collection process for each study-side.

Table 1: Case studies

Country, Partner, Scale	Case Study Name	Primary Data Collection & Timeframe	Data Collection progress so far
Portugal FS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Region of Alentejo City of Évora 	Resilience in long term care facilities of different socio-economic status: COVID-19 structural and psychosocial impacts on elderly residents in Évora, Portugal	Semi-structured Interviews: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> May 2022 to August 2022 Vulnerable Target Population: Elderly living in long term care facilities (LTCF; Private vs. Public vs. Third Sector) ≥ 15 (≥ 5 per type of LTCF) LTCF Administration ≥ 12 (≥ 4 per type of LTCF) LTCF Workers ≥ 12 (≥ 4 per type of LTCF) Quantitative Surveys (if possible): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> October 2022 to February 2022 \geq Same sample of LTCF recruited for interviews 	Portugal: 45 completed interviews: 20 LTFC elderly, 12 LTCF workers, 13 LTCF technical directors.
Belgium UANTWERPEN <ul style="list-style-type: none"> City of Antwerp Neighbourhoods: Borgerhout and Antwerpen Noord	Mental health impacts, needs and responses among migrant communities during the COVID-19 pandemic: a qualitative case study in Antwerp, Belgium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The population that is the primary focus of the case study are members of migrant communities in Borgerhout and Antwerpen Noord, specifically migrants that arrived in Belgium more than 5 years ago. Participants are recruited through organisations or actors working with migrants in Borgerhout and Antwerpen Noord, and via snowball sampling. In addition to this target population, we will engage with three additional groups of participants, linked to work packages 4, 5 and 6: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP4 link: representatives from local-level government and decision makers (Stad Antwerpen) WP5 link: professionals working in (mental) health services: GPs, psychologists, psychiatrists, councillors, etc. WP6 link: representatives from community-level initiatives and services (e.g. Coronababbels, Atlas vzw, De Borgerhoutse hulplijn) Approximate sample sizes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Key informant/expert interviews: $n \geq 15$ Interviews with migrants living in Borgerhout and Antwerpen Noord: $n \geq 20/25$ 	13 interviews with experts and 20 interviews with migrants.
Spain URJC & SAMUR	Experiences with social protection of vulnerable Latin American and Moroccan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The sample is composed of 10 interviews with the migrant population, focusing on the two largest migrant communities in Madrid, that is, the Latin American community and the Moroccan community. 	10 citizens, 5 decision makers and 5

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> City of Madrid 	communities in Madrid	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To be representative, the sample is composed of 6 Latin American respondents and 4 Moroccan respondents. The sample also considers a 50%-50% male-female balance (i.e., 3 Latin American men and 3 Latin American women; and 2 Moroccan men and 2 Moroccan women); The fieldwork was carried out between May and July 2022. 	NGOs interviewed.
Italy SAPIENZA & UCSC <ul style="list-style-type: none"> City of Rome Agostino Gemelli University Hospital	The impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on the well-being of healthcare workers (Healthcare workers)	Quantitative Surveys: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> September 2022 to December 2022 At least at least 100 physicians and 200 nurses; Semi structured interviews: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> November 2022-February 2023 Minimum number of participants is n>14. 	Quantitative survey: pre-test done. Survey done:722 individual interviews collected
Austria SYNYO <ul style="list-style-type: none"> City of Vienna 	Experiences of women working at the frontline of in social supermarkets in Vienna, Austria	Three branches in neighbourhoods are selected with varying demographic compositions to get a better understanding of the role of customers in the supermarket environment. Additionally, we will choose supermarkets that also vary in their size and layout. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Minimum number of interviews with frontline workers: total of 6-8 interviews; Minimum number of interviews with managers: total of 4 interviews (1-2 interviews with staff in supervisors, management or sustainability roles); Data collection started in January 2023 and is foreseen to last approximately until the end of February 2023. 	2 management interview conducted 1 Frontline workers interview conducted
Germany SINUS Sweden UGOT Germany <ul style="list-style-type: none"> City of Mannheim Neighbourhoods: Neckartadt-West; Schöna 	Information seeking among ethnic minorities and socio-economic vulnerable groups in Sweden and Germany related to the implementation of protective measures and vaccination willingness	The primary data collection focuses on the neighbourhood scale from 2020 to 2022. Total number of migrants 24 across both sites. The total number of stakeholders working with migrants is 16 across both sites. The total sample is therefore 40 across both sites. Primary data will be analysed and interpreted in the context of secondary data on the municipal and national scales; The sample overlaps with WP4-7. The sample plan is designed to enable: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1) comparison by migration background within WP4-7 (6 females and 6 males without migration background; and 6 females and 6 males with migration background); 	None completed yet.

<p>u; Jungbush/ Inn enstadt Sweden</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> City of Gothenburg Neighbourhoods: Bergsjön; Hjällbo 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2) comparison by gender within the case study (WP3). 	
<p>Greece KEMEA</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> City of Athens & Thessaloniki 	<p>Policing in times of pandemic: impact on the role of LEAs, governmental actors and policy makers and its effect on trust issues of minority groups (migrants, refugees, and Roma communities) towards the former in Greece</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interviews will be scheduled with representatives from governmental institutions and LEAs, as well as with officials from well-known NGOs that deal with vulnerable populations or minorities housed under those (N=10 interviews in total, 5 of each); The recruiting period as well as the site visits to conduct the interviews and the transcripts, analysis etc. will last approximately about 3 months. 	<p>- 5 LEAs and 5 representatives of migrants interviewed.</p>
<p>Wales SU</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wales City of Swansea 	<p>The multiplicity of BAME migrant nurses' vulnerabilities in South Wales</p>	<p>Qualitative interviews:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 8 BAME overseas qualified nurses 8 healthcare managers who work with BAME overseas qualified nurses Data collection: until 1 February 2023 <p>Creative workshops:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 6-12 BAME overseas qualified nurses (one or two sessions) Data collection: until 1 February 2023 <p>Quantitative survey:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 171 BAME residents in the Swansea Metropolitan Area Data collection: finished 	<p>- 3 nurses are interviewed</p> <p>- 6 healthcare managers are interviewed</p> <p>- the quantitative survey has been conducted with 171 BAME residents in Swansea Metropolitan Area</p>

England MDI TRI Ireland TRI	Hard-to-reach communities (ethnic and religious minorities) in England	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Instead of searching for a representative sample, and trying to go through every ethnicity and every religion in England, interviews will be conducted with people who have a story to tell; • Identification and selection of storytellers will be based on the researchers' engagement with the community as journalists and members of civil society organisations. 	31 interviews have been collected in England with people belonging to ethnic or religious minorities

4 Methodological reflections

The evolution of the COVID-19 virus and pandemic, and its ongoing insights, also brings along considerable impacts on the methodology of the project, ranging from difficulties to reach people, conducting face-to-face interviews, ethics concerning online interviewing, and overburdened professionals that encounter difficulties making time to participate in research. This section will now set out the methodological experiences of empirical research. This will cover both the resident interviews and the case studies. Whilst the resident interview target group (women from a lower socioeconomic background) is not one which was explicitly focused on in the case studies, for some partners these still overlapped. Furthermore, because both the case study and the resident interviews focused on vulnerable groups, the experience of collecting data faced many similar challenges and successes. Additionally, the task of focusing on case studies was inherently challenging yet innovative to integrate within complex system theory. Selecting relevant topics in each research site in order to study the vulnerabilities of each complex system posed challenges for comparability across the different research sites.

The main challenge for both the resident interviews and the case studies was difficulties with recruitment. Nevertheless, given the overall difficulties to contact people and extra burdens the COVID-19 pandemic has put on many people's lives, for a variety of reasons, it was at the same time surprising that we managed to recruit this many participants. Certainly, given that at the time of the proposal writing, the duration of the COVID-19 pandemic was expected to be much shorter and expected to be in much more control at the time the fieldwork would be conducted, that was actually the case. Nonetheless, we encountered some delays in collecting data for both the resident interviews and the case studies. Limited resources and a typically overlooked target group meant that this was a time-consuming exercise. The most practical way respondents were found was through CSOs or NGOs from which they seek assistance. This was a requirement for the resident interviews but was also the approach taken by many partners for the case study, although a limitation is that the most vulnerable populations may not have taken the steps to reach out to organisations for help. Nonetheless, it helped a lot to gain the trust of the interviewees and to ensure that they felt comfortable with the interview. Further examples of recruitment techniques include using a collaborator to put a call out to her various WhatsApp groups in order to recruit participants (SWANSEA), visiting social supermarkets (SYNYO) and engaging with community health workers as 'gate-keepers' (UANTWERPEN). Community health workers had many contacts and were well-trusted with the target groups. Approaching the respondent

with an 'insider' helped to build up a rapport before asking to conduct an interview. However, this depended heavily on the goodwill of the organisation or community workers helping, and many did not respond to emails or phone calls. A more hands-on approach was therefore beneficial, going to organisations directly and asking them face-to-face.

Conducting the interviews in CSO spaces or in cafes in the respondent's neighbourhood helped facilitate their willingness to talk openly. However, this also depended on the space of the CSO. A busy 'drop in' for an organisation, where respondents were going for support with urgent practical issues may have been less appropriate than a quieter place where respondents were going for coffee and to socialise. This is so they felt less pressured to participate and could take the time to chat first. It was also beneficial to join activities with the target group unrelated to the research, in order to help gain trust and contacts in the field. But of course, this demands time. The process was sometimes emotionally draining, convincing often busy residents to take the time to be interviewed whilst ensuring they were not put under pressure.

Another challenge in conducting the interviews was the schedules of residents, who tend to have precarious jobs with long and inflexible working hours, which made it impossible to schedule interviews on working days. These would then need to be conducted on weekends. Furthermore, some interviews took place in public spaces such as cafes. This meant there was a lot of background noise, and for some partners, this meant transcribing them was more taxing.

Another challenge highlighted by the partners related to language barriers. For both the resident interviews and case studies, many respondents were migrants with a limited level of the host country's language. This caused difficulties during recruitment, but also with a misunderstanding of questions which limited their ability to talk more extensively and deeply about the topics asked. Whilst this could sometimes be addressed with the help of a translator, this was not always possible for partners. It was important to ensure that the interview guide was in simple language, and did not use jargon or unnecessary academic concepts. Sometimes the interview guide needed to be adapted as a consequence. Furthermore, in the Portuguese case study (FS), during interviews with the elderly, there were some issues relating to hearing that meant it was difficult to engage in a fluid conversation. Some respondents were already sceptical of the COVID-19 pandemic measures or the government. Therefore, it was vital to first build up trust, with someone close by who could explain it properly in their mother tongue, and assure them that everything remained anonymous. However, it was important not to proceed with the interview if the respondent was too uncertain, to ensure they were not feeling pressured into doing something they did not fully understand.

Working with organisations or bridging links to the target population helped the respondent to feel more comfortable speaking openly. It helped to avoid stigma and uncomfortable situations for the women seeking help. This helped with positionality issues and to address some of the power imbalances which exist. Some women were also more comfortable being interviewed by a woman. For instance, being able to attend a group for women of Moroccan background in poverty and join many of their activities in Antwerp (Belgium) was only possible because the interviewer was a woman. However, mostly the interviewer had no migration background or low socio-economic status. Being from a different ethnicity and having a higher income means that there was a power relationship which could have affected willingness to participate or responses in terms of social desirability. All teams face similar issues and try in similar ways to negotiate their access to the field.

Looking back, some partners felt that it would be beneficial to use an in-person approach for recruitment. Being on-site in the local community and contacting grass-roots organisations in person (not only by phone or mail) could have helped to recruit respondents faster, as many CSOs did not respond or took a long time to respond. Although it was insisted that respondents recall their experience in the different phases, perhaps because of the emotional trauma of the pandemic, most respondents recalled their experience during confinement in particular, so it was also useful to include pointers for the different waves or lockdowns.

Despite the challenges and limitations, partners managed to recruit a diverse group of respondents. Partners also highlight that those interviewed so far have been detailed with the information provided in response to questions. Respondents were very willing to share their experiences of COVID-19, and there were a variety of honest and thought-provoking responses from interviewees. The richness of the data resulted in more unexpected outcomes, truly honouring the added value of qualitative research when dealing with this research question.

5 Data analyses and future plans

The issues explored in the case studies complement the empirical research carried out in WPs 4-7 as they allow for a more in-depth exploration of specific aspects of the cross-cutting issues among specific impacted populations, within the areas of government (WP4), public health (WP5), community (WP6), and information policy (WP7). Data analysis on the aforementioned aspects will later provide input for policy recommendations in WP8. A case study coordination guidelines update will be published in January 2023 (D3.7). Between May and June 2023, findings will be synthesised and guidelines will be identified with best practices for future pandemics. In August 2023, D3.8 will include a comparative report of final case studies. Furthermore, the case study data analysis will inspire academic papers and other non-scientific publications such as policy briefs.

Regarding the resident interviews, the analysis will feed into D.x.7 and D.x.8. D.x.7 provides an analysis for each work package (for example public health responses and impact for WP5). A synthesis and lessons learnt on each work package entail the D.x.8 deliverables. Similarly, the data collected for the resident interviews will be further analysed in more focused academic and non-scientific publications beyond the concrete WP deliverables.

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